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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. KRESTER M. DIAZ

Assistant Professor IV

Negros Oriental State University

kresterm Diaz@gmail.com

“THE SHIFTING SANDS OF PHILIPPINE LANGUAGE POLICY”

Filipino has come full-circle prick the national consciousness and lay its vexing burden at the feet of our national planners, as well as of the academe (Rubrico, 1986). Philippines, as we know, is a multilingual nation with over one hundred dialects spoken as auxiliary official in their respective regions. Stevens (1999) adds that over the course of its development, Tagalog and other languages of the Philippines have been influenced by Chinese, Japanese, Spanish, English, and many other languages, in trade and in occupations by various countries. He also states that Tagalog and other local languages have taken and adapted words from all of these languages to make them part of their own languages but still maintained their own languages and separations from one language to another.

The fact that the Philippines is a multilingual nation, it is very necessary for language planners to decide about language policies, requirements, and practices in all social contexts Filipinos should use and follow for the expressed purpose of solving any communication problems. The decisions will influence the right to use and maintain languages, affect language status, and determine which languages are nurtured. Thus, language policy and planning decisions really have a major impact on shaping the direction and nature of change in language, and of course, on the rights of the individual.

Bilingualism in the Philippines

The 1986 EDSA Revolution catapulted into power the first woman president, Corazon Aquino, who restored democracy through the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines. The constitution declares Filipino as the national language and reiterates the position of English as an official language of the country. As before, both were to serve as languages of instruction (Sugbo in Celis 2009).

According to Espiritu (2015), the Language provision in the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines which are embodied in Article XIV, Sec. 6 and 7 provide the legal basis implemented in the country. The provisions are as follows:

1. Section 6. The National language of the Philippines is Filipino. As it evolves, it shall be further developed and enriched on the basis of existing Philippine and other languages.
2. For purposes of communication and instruction, the official languages of the Philippines are Filipino and, until otherwise provided by law, English.

From the provisions mentioned above, the Department of Education, Culture and Sports (DECS) then issued Dept. Order No. 25, s. 1974 titled, “Implementing Guidelines for the Policy on Bilingual Education.” As defined by Espiritu (2015), Bilingual Education is defined operationally as the

separate use of Filipino and English as the media of instruction in specific subject areas. DECS Order No. 25 stipulates that Pilipino (changed to Filipino in 1987) shall be used as medium of instruction in social studies/social sciences, music, arts, physical education, home economics, practical arts and character education while science, mathematics, and technology subjects will make use of English.

Celis (2009) enumerated the goals of the Bilingual Education Policy and they are as follows:

1. Enhanced learning through two languages to achieve quality education as called for by the 1987 Constitution;
2. The propagation of Filipino as a language of literacy;
3. The development of Filipino as a linguistic symbol of National unity and identity;
4. The cultivation and elaboration of Filipino as a language of scholarly discourse, that is to say, its continuing intellectualization; and the maintenance of English as an international language for the Philippines and as a non-exclusive language of science and technology.

On the effects of bilingual instruction on the literacy skills of young learners in a study conducted by Aquino (2012), he inferred that monolingual instruction in either Filipino or English had a stronger effect on the children's literacy skills compared to bilingual instruction. Results showed that mother tongue-based instruction had stronger effect on the learners' literacy skills.

Garbes (2012) pointed out that the idea of students not completely using the mother tongue is both psychologically and culturally damaging. In effect, students will increasingly view their own native language as irrelevant. That is why the reformed DepEd has sought to address this criticism and pushed a bill through Congress that completely overhauls the current educational system starting 2012. "The first is the extension of secondary school. Prior to 2011, there was a 10-year long education cycle. With this bill, the Philippines will adopt a K-12 cycle to ensure that students are prepared to go to university by the time of graduation from grade 12.

Mother-tongue Based and K-12 Policies

DepEd Order 31, s.2012 stipulates that Mother Tongue shall be used as a medium of instruction and as a subject from Grades 1 to 3. English or Filipino shall be used from Grades 4 to 10.

"The use of the same language spoken at home, in the early grades, helps improve the pupils' language and cognitive development in addition to strengthening their socio-cultural awareness," Education Secretary Armin Luistro said in a statement in Rappler.

Ronquillo (2016) also talked on the use of mother tongue based education where she articulated that with MTB-MLE, we expand the access to social, political, economic and physical development processes, which are often unreachable for children who speak a different mother tongue. She added that children find it hard to learn about their society. She believed that the core benefits of MTB-MLE will encourage children to become lifelong learners by urging them to be confident, accepting, and enthusiastic about their cultural heritage.

Each Filipino with hopes to compete in a global context will have to take the enhanced K to 12 Basic Education Program which seeks to provide for a quality 12 – year basic education program This is in cognizance with Article IV Section 2 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution which states that: "The state shall establish, maintain, and support a complete, adequate, and integrated system of education relevant to the needs of the people and society".

As Daquioag (2012) put it, "The goal of the enhanced K to 12 Basic Education Program is to create a functional basic education system that will produce productive and responsible citizens equipped

with the essential competencies and skills for both life – long learning and employment.” He also said that the program will enhance the basic education system to full functionality to fulfil the basic learning needs of students which is in line with the agenda of President Benigno Aquino III of having quality education as a long term solution to poverty. In order to achieve these goals, the program has the following twin – objectives:

- a.) To give every student an opportunity to receive quality education based on an enhanced and decongested curriculum that is internationally recognized and comparable;
- b.) To change public perception that high school education is just a preparation for college; rather than, it should allow one to take advantage of opportunities for gainful career or employment and/or self - employment in a rapidly changing and increasingly globalized environment.

In my own personal stance about the overhaul of K-12 education system from Bilingual education, the new system will help market our students in an increasingly global job market or even put them at par with the rest of the world.

However, I just don't buy the idea of using mother tongue as a medium of instruction for reasons like to help our students appreciate our cultural heritage even more. If we want to produce quality students who can compete in the international arena, why not start exposing them to the international language so they may not have difficulty adjusting to the language in the long run? I understand that an individual's language has a profound impact on his cognitive processes, but if we remove English as a medium of instruction in our schools, there is a tendency that lower-income students will never learn to speak English at all compared to the well-to-do whose parents can find alternative means of education to expose them to the language. My point is we can be fluent in Filipino without sacrificing English.

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